

WALNUT AND VEGETABLES PRODUCTION WITHIN AF SYSTEMS

1. Walnut and Leek 2. Cabbage row at Tolhurst Organics, UK (AGROFORWARD) 3. Beetroot in agroforestry (Inagro)

WHAT AND WHY

Agroforestry combines woody, perennial crops with the cultivation of agricultural crops or livestock. Walnut trees are particularly well suited for agroforestry with vegetables due to their deep root system, slow growth, open crown, and late leaf development. These traits result in minimal competition for light and water, which is crucial for healthy and profitable vegetable production. The growing demand for locally and sustainably produced vegetables makes agroforestry with walnut trees an attractive and forward-looking farming approach. Combining vegetables such as cabbage, beans, leeks, or root crops with walnut trees creates a more productive, diverse, and climate-resilient cropping environment. For optimal yields, it is important to select walnut varieties that ensure good cross-pollination and are well adapted to local soil and climate conditions. When tree rows, spacing, and crop rotations are carefully planned, farmers can not only diversify their production but also contribute to soil improvement, carbon sequestration, and landscape enhancement.

Keywords: Walnut trees, Vegetable cultivation, Local production, Variety selection, Biodiversity, Productive tree strips

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

Crop selection largely determines the success of agroforestry systems combining vegetables and trees. Early crops such as spinach, kohlrabi, and summer, autumn, or winter leeks compete little with trees for light and water. Walnut trees perform well on airy, deep, and well-drained soils, but are best avoided on wet soils with a high water table. In the initial phase, when the trees are not yet productive, the tree rows can be temporarily used for crops like pumpkin, rhubarb, or artichoke. This increases the profitability of the system during the start-up phase. Choosing the right walnut variety is essential: late-leaving varieties only develop foliage later in the season, reducing shade pressure on the crops underneath. This provides an additional growth advantage for light-sensitive vegetable crops.

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ADVANTAGES

Walnut trees are particularly well suited for agroforestry when planted on well-drained, airy, and deep soils, as they do not tolerate high groundwater levels. Depending on the intended purpose, such as nut or timber production, a suitable variety and pruning method should be selected. Late-leaving varieties are beneficial in combination with vegetable crops because they cause less shading early in the growing season. Proper pollination is essential for optimal yields. When tree rows are combined with grasses and herbs, they create valuable habitats for natural pest controllers like insects, birds, and other beneficial species. This increases biodiversity and makes the farming system more resilient, reducing the need for pesticides. Trees offer shelter and food for wildlife, reinforcing natural pest control. The leaf fall of walnut trees contributes to soil organic matter and enhances carbon storage. At the same time, the trees help regulate the local microclimate by moderating heat, reducing evaporation, and retaining soil moisture during increasingly frequent hot periods. As a result, food forests and agroforestry systems become more resistant to climate extremes. Agroforestry is especially attractive for small-scale farms such as organic, CSA, or pick-your-own operations, which typically use manual labor and light machinery, making tree rows less of a barrier. For these farms, the visual quality of crops, which can sometimes be affected by shading, is less critical than for large-scale or industrial buyers. Finally, agroforestry aligns with the sustainability goals of small-scale farming initiatives and can be an added asset in their marketing strategy. The potential for product diversification also strengthens the farm's economic resilience.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Walnut trees are ideal for agroforestry with vegetables due to their open crown and late leaf development, which results in minimal shading and competition.**
- **The cultivation of vegetables such as cabbages, beans, leeks, and root crops experiences little to no interference from tree rows.**
- **Offers small-scale farmers greater product diversification and economic resilience.**

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